

Interactive Dashboard for the Integration of Spatiotemporal LULC and Agricultural Multisource Mapping Datasets: Structure, Implementation, and Visualization

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Abstract

This article aims to develop an interactive dashboard for qualitative and quantitative analysis of mapping products provided by different land use and land cover (LULC) mapping initiatives, with a primary focus on agricultural information. A modular and scalable methodology was proposed to achieve this goal, based on the development of a robust methodological workflow using the Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) process, capable of ensuring transparency, reproducibility, flexibility, accessibility, and quality in data presentation. The methodology employs stages of metadata translation, data cleaning, unified processing with data standardization and categorization, generation of auxiliary structures for spatiotemporal statistical analyses, graphical visualization, and quality validation. The results demonstrate the dashboard's capability to centralize and manage information, providing to users an integrated interface with appropriate visualizations and meaningful analyses tailored to support the decision-making process.

Keywords - Land Cover, Land Use, Agriculture, ETL, Multitemporal Analysis

1 Introduction

Recent technological advances in geoinformation and remote sensing have made the production, distribution, and access to open data from land use and land cover (LULC) mapping initiatives at various levels of representation and coverage increasingly accessible [7]. However, the heterogeneous and decentralized mass of data originating from multiple sources can hinder analysts' decision-making processes and prompt questions about which products are most appropriate for a given research field (e.g., agriculture) [8].

In this context, interactive dashboards [1] have emerged as powerful tools for efficiently and effectively exploiting large volumes of information, particularly in education and scientific research [3, 4]. Dashboards facilitate centralized organization, management, integrated analysis, and rapid pattern-and-trend detection in data through optimized, dynamic, and time-efficient workflows [1, 6]. They can swiftly, almost in real time, flag inconsistencies and visually highlight salient information by generating graphical visualizations and calculating meaningful statistical metrics tailored to specific objectives [1, 6]. The system also allows additional information to be appended to the core dataset without repeating the entire analysis workflow, thereby supporting continuous monitoring and incremental updates [1, 6].

This work aims to develop an interactive dashboard that compiles open LULC and agricultural mapping datasets to produce spatiotemporal analyses that potentially enhance the cognitive tasks of organizing,

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monitoring, managing, and making decisions. The motivation for the dashboard creation was the need to consolidate scattered information on LULC mapping products, streamlining comparison, analysis, and decision-making. Centered on agricultural applications in Brazil, the dashboard is designed to assemble textual and analytical information that supports the evaluation of these products.

2 Material and Methods

The integrated data in this study originate from remote sensing LULC products provided by thirteen different initiatives, each presenting distinct characteristics and levels of map representation, as described in [8]. Supplementary relevant data (e.g., spectral and spatial resolutions) were also incorporated into the dataset.

The LANDAGRI-B dashboard was developed using an Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) workflow tailored to the characteristics of the input data, which involved spatio-temporal analyses of land use and land cover products across different coverage levels, with an emphasis on agricultural applications in Brazil. This methodology is rooted in a modular, hierarchical, scalable, and data-driven architecture, designed to ensure the robustness, reproducibility, and flexibility of the analyses performed.

The implementation began with data intake and organization, compiling the principal features of LULC mapping products. Metadata were stored in JSONC files, with comments and documentation included for each initiative to promote understanding and maintainability. The next stage involved data interpretation and cleaning, carried out by a specialized module responsible for removing comments, validating file structures, and parsing complex fields, such as spatial resolution, accuracy, reference systems, and time series. This module also automatically categorized classification methodologies, standardized nomenclature, and normalized input formats to ensure data consistency.

Next, a unified processing component integrated the parsed data and performed integrity, consistency, and completeness checks. At this juncture, quantitative metrics (e.g., resolution and accuracy scores), automatic detection of temporal gaps, and auxiliary structures (e.g., comparison matrices and time-series analyses) were generated to support analytics. The processing pipeline further produced descriptive statistics and classified the initiatives by geographic scope (global, continental, national, and regional levels), methodology (sensor resolution, accuracy, classifier type), and temporal dimensions (frequency, coverage), all filterable through the user interface. To enhance performance and user experience, the processed data were encapsulated in an access layer, known as the data wrapper, which implements multi-level caching, thus enabling efficient loading and reuse of intermediate outputs. This layer also prepared data for various visualization types, including comparative, temporal, and detailed charts.

Data visualization was accomplished through an interactive Streamlit interface featuring modular components for results navigation, filtering, and exploration. All graphical outputs were generated with the

Figure 1. Interactive dashboard generation flowchart.

Plotly library, ensuring visual interactivity and responsiveness. The system includes an automated validation and data quality reporting. The adapted ETL workflow is illustrated in Figure 1.

Throughout, best practices in software engineering were observed, guided by Python Enhancement Proposals (PEPs) 8 and 257 [9, 10], including separation of concerns (with each module dedicated to a specific role), rigorous documentation, type hints for easier maintenance, and coding standardization. This approach guarantees the system’s extensibility, facilitating future incorporation of new datasets, analytical methods, and visualization features, and ensuring both transparency and reproducibility of the dashboard analyses. The dashboard was implemented locally in VSCode v.1.102.1 using Python v.3.12.2 and Markdown languages. GitHub Copilot [2], GPT-4.1 model [5], and Context7 Model Context Protocol (MCP) server supported code writing, refactoring, debugging and optimization. The dashboard is hosted in an open-source application at Streamlit’s programming interface.

3 Results and Discussion

The primary sources for assembling the dashboard’s dataset included scientific articles, technical reports, and official websites associated with LULC mapping initiatives. The information collected was initially compiled in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format with comments (".jsonc"), thereby enabling seamless semantic integration of the data into the system, independent of the programming language implemented. These data were subsequently transformed, resulting in four metadata files (Table 1).

Metadata Files	Description	Mapping Type
<i>Initiatives</i>	Structured database of thirteen land use and land cover mapping initiatives	LULC
<i>Sensors</i>	Detailed technical specifications of sensors characteristics	LULC
<i>Availability</i>	CONAB ¹ agricultural data temporal availability of different crops types, discriminated by cropping year and Brazilian states	Agriculture
<i>Crop Calendar</i>	CONAB detailed agricultural calendar of sowing and harvesting crop periods, discriminated by crop type and Brazilian states	Agriculture
<i>IBGE Agricultural Data</i>	IBGE ² detailed agricultural data estimates of brazilian main temporary and permanent crops	Agriculture

CONAB¹ = National Supply Company; IBGE² = Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics.

Table 1. Dataset metadata files information.

The structural components of the dashboard were organized into three main modules: **Overview**, **Initiative Analysis**, and **Agricultural Analysis** (Figure 2). In addition, the dashboard comprises the **About** module, which outlines its objectives, provides guidance for navigating the specialized modules, and presents relevant references concerning the datasets and the project.

The Overview module provides a general summary of LULC mapping initiatives, presenting the main characteristics of the products. Subsequently, the Initiative Analysis module provides tabular and graphical information on the products based on detailed qualitative and quantitative temporal analyses. Finally, the Agricultural Analysis module offers temporal analyses of the main agricultural crops practiced in Brazil, with tabular and graphical information available to users. All modules feature active filtering functionality that allows users to iteratively select one or more initiatives of interest for information extraction and comparisons.

The implemented analysis addressed aspects of the data such as performance metrics, trends, temporal gaps, temporal evolution, temporal availability, and timeline chronology. Based on these, several graphical elements were produced, including bar charts, pie charts, radar charts, and heat maps. In this way, the dashboard enables users to visually interpret and assess the data compatibility and comparability, as well as to identify trends over time. An overview of the initial interface and some of the dashboard’s generated results are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. The dashboard is available at the following link: <https://landagri-bdashboard.streamlit.app>.

Figure 2. Dashboard structure and resulting interface.

(a) Monthly seasonality analysis by crops.

(b) Initiatives methodology distribution.

(c) Heatmap of the Brazilian crops agricultural calendar.

(d) Multidimensional comparison radar chart of five initiatives.

Figure 3. Selected results pertaining to LULC analysis and agricultural dynamics.

4 Conclusions

In this research the LANDAGRI-B dashboard was developed, providing an interactive platform that integrates spatiotemporal LULC mapping and agricultural informations from multisource data. The proposed ETL-based methodology demonstrated effectiveness in consolidating heterogeneous and decentralized data sources through a modular, scalable architecture that ensures transparency, reproducibility, and data quality. The three-module structure provided users with diverse comprehensive filtering and visualization functionalities, enabling efficient analysis of LULC products for informed decision-making processes.

The LANDAGRI-B dashboard represents a valuable contribution to LULC data centralization, management, integration and visualization, providing robust foundations and capabilities for enhanced analytical utilization of open geospatial datasets in land monitoring applications. This work is part of the first author's PhD thesis project. Therefore, its scope is flexible and may undergo modifications in future work.

For forthcoming research, this project intends to incorporate vector-based spatial data to facilitate the spatial representation of information and support iterative geospatial navigation across the Brazilian territory. This integration will enable users to visually interpret the agricultural patterns distribution, thereby enhancing geospatial analytical assessments capacity and augmenting physical contextual understanding.

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